

Effects of hormones on callus induction from mature seeds of rice.^a

Hormone (mg L ⁻¹)	Callus Induction frequency (%)	Callus characteristics
NAA (4) + 2,4-D (1) + kinetin (0.2)	20.8	Pale yellow; some calli with root hairs
2,4-D (2) + kinetin (0.2)	24.2	Globular, compact, and yellow

^aBasic medium used was Murashige and Skoog (MS).

frequency was slightly higher and calli were fresh yellow, compact, and globular when supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ and 0.2 mg Kin L⁻¹ (see table).

Effect of culturing procedures. When calli reached 1-2 mm in diameter, half were transferred into AA, MS, and N6 liquid media supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ and 0.2 mg Kin L⁻¹ and shaken at 120 rpm.

The other half was subcultured onto the same induction medium with 500 mg proline L⁻¹ for 10 d to 6 mo (subcultured once a month) and then transferred into liquid suspension culture. Calli turned brown and died in 3-4 d in liquid culture with immediate transfer or subculture for less than 1 mo. On the other hand, calli could propagate quickly when transferred

into liquid media after subculture on solid induction media for 1 mo or longer. At the start of suspension culture, the calli were subcultured every 3 d by replacing all original medium with the same fresh medium. After 4 wk, the aggregates grew well, and cultures were subcultured every 6 d by replacing two-thirds of the original medium with the same fresh medium. Subsequently, the well-grown cultures released many miniclusters into the liquid medium. Thus, through about 3 mo of suspension culture, we obtained embryogenic cell suspensions composed mainly of cell aggregates consisting of 10-60 cells with fresh yellow color and dense cytoplasm. ■

Factors affecting pollen embryogenesis of rice anther culture

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Anther culture techniques as a means of breeding are considered effective and time-saving methods for obtaining pure linea in rice and for other major crop improvement.

Pollen embryogenesis is believed to provide new prospects for anther culture because of its stability and enhanced recovery of regenerants.

We occasionally observed pollen embryogenesis during rice anther culture in many cultivars and F₁ plants in our laboratory. Growth regulators, water stress, and media composition affect the induction rate of pollen embryogenesis (Torrizo and Zapata 1986).

Abscisic acid (ABA) in the callus formation medium was most effective for pollen embryogenesis of rice; callus formation from the anthers plated did not increase significantly. However, embryo formations were markedly increased.

Table 1. Effects of abscisic acid (ABA) on embryo and callus formation in rice anther culture.

ABA (mg L ⁻¹)	Responding anthers (%)	Calli formed (%)	Embryos formed (%)
0	19.7 ± 2.3 ^a	8.4 ± 1.1	1.6 ± 0.4
0.5	28.8 ± 2.2	9.1 ± 1.1	10.8 ± 1.2
1.0	19.7 ± 2.1	7.2 ± 1.2	7.2 ± 0.8
5.0	18.1 ± 1.8	6.6 ± 1.0	8.8 ± 0.9
10.0	15.1 ± 1.6	7.3 ± 0.9	5.5 ± 0.9
20.0	7.8 ± 1.4	2.9 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 0.5

^aMean ± SE.

Table 2. Effects of growth regulators on germination of pollen embryos in rice anther culture.

Growth regulators (mg L ⁻¹)			Plants (%)	
Zeatin	IAA ^a	Kinetin	Green	Albino
1	0	0	6.1 ± 2.0 ^b	5.0 ± 5.0
5	0	0	13.9 ± 3.9	5.0 ± 5.0
1	0.2	0	8.6 ± 1.8	2.0 ± 2.0
5	0.2	0	9.8 ± 0.2	0
0	0.5	2	26.7 ± 1.9	0
0	0	0	8.0 ± 1.0	8.0 ± 5.8

^aIAA = indole acetic acid. ^bMean ± SE.

Maximum frequency (10.8%) of embryo formation was obtained at 0.5 ppm ABA (Table 1). Also, ABA treatment during the cold pretreatment period (15 °C, 15 d) showed the same tendency as that under *in vitro* condition.

We tested several combinations of plant growth regulators for germinating pollen embryos. The combination of 0.5 ppm

indole acetic acid and 2.0 ppm kinetin was suitable for germinating embryos (Table 2).

The results indicate that ABA is important in plant regeneration and embryo formation in rice anther culture.

Cited reference

Torrizo LB, Zapata FJ. 1986. Anther culture of rice. IV. The effect of abscisic acid on plant regeneration. *Plant Cell Rep.* 5:136-139. ■